

TEACHER PERSONALITY IN THE IMPROVING ENGLISH TEACHING METHODOLOGY

Umarova Feruza Nigmatovna

Senior Teacher, English Department,

‘TIAME’ National Research University, Tashkent, Uzbekistan

ANNOTATION

This qualitative study relies heavily on a critical analysis of scholarly thought and work on the importance of teaching methodology and its relationship to language teacher personality. Based on a pragmatic investigation of the research topic, this study puts forward ideas on teaching methodology and personal characteristics to produce more competent teachers of English.

Key words: *Teaching English, teachers, teaching methodologies, teacher personality, teaching style*

Introduction

The primary role of teachers is to deliver instructions and content to students. The secondary role of teachers is to teach in a way that engages students and ensures optimal performance. In teaching English Language, it is essential to ensure that instructions given to students are clear. One key role played by the teacher is ‘motivation.’ Motivation plays a definitive role in learning, in general. Motivated learners are enthusiastic, goal-oriented, committed, persistent, and confident learners (Renandya, 2012). Both of these roles (traditional and new pedagogies) have to co-exist. While traditional roles are cognizant of sound educational principles, new pedagogies introduce ‘motivation’ as a really important aspect of language teaching (Lamb, 2017). A teacher should be a motivator rather than a controller. On the traditional role continuum, a teacher is also a resource. The teacher is a resource in that

he introduces a lesson, which was previously unknown to students. The teacher explains difficult grammar concepts and vocabulary. It is also the responsibility of the instructor to coordinate group activities. Classroom sociologists have found that incorporating humane activities into teaching activities enhances learning in all aspects (Fernandez, 2003).

Methodology

Teachers' personal traits are examined qualitatively rather than quantitatively. The main variables recognized in teacher personalities are linked to the ability to understand students' learning problems, background knowledge of the students, and positive or negative attitude towards teaching (Hashim, Alam, & Yusoff, 2014).

Participants

In many studies, the outcome of this variable or the dependent factor is the performance of students; also named the ability of students to be able to interact freely with their teachers as one of these characteristics. Most of all, many studies have emphasized that teachers need to combine both curricular knowledge and pedagogical.

Data Collection and Analysis

In a foreign English language class, it is important that the teacher has a prepared mindset to teach English language to students from varying backgrounds. According to Hashim, Alam et al. (2014), the following interpersonal traits: high levels of discipline, coping with diversity, and having a positive attitude are also important traits. Teachers are expected to adapt lesson contents into practical activities for students and judge intellectual and language development. All these improve students' performance when carried out properly. Typically, students' development and self-confidence are always influenced by teachers' attitudes. The present study examines the roles of teachers in terms of the methodologies that they use in classrooms, and suggests how teachers have to change their personal whims and fancies with regard to teaching and develop a personality and choose a methodology that they are going to use in a language classroom. Holding a good degree does not necessarily associate with being a good teacher. Rather, many other qualities are pertinent. Quite necessarily, a good

teacher needs to have personal effectiveness, interaction skills, and intercession skills, which are collectively known as people skills alongside traditional teaching skills. And to teach the English language in a non-native context, ‘global skills’ (Haines, 2019) is a necessity. This skill includes abilities of communication and collaboration, creativity and critical thinking, intercultural competence, and emotional self-regulation and wellbeing, which empower one to work in an international setting. It also includes cultural awareness and language and communication skills. The English Language has been continually taught in many more regions of the world. It is the role of stakeholders to influence the necessary competency level required for teachers in all aspects of teaching. Stakeholders in English Language teaching include students, administrators, and other teachers. It is the role of policymakers (administrators) to define the required competencies (Arkoudis & Tran, 2010). Miller (2012), in her research work, summarized the characteristics of a good teacher as possessing enthusiasm, creativeness, spurring students to learn, displaying a positive attitude towards teaching, having good content knowledge, and imparting equal treatment to all students. Beyond ‘good’ is ‘great’. A teacher can go from ‘good’ to ‘great’ by including personal human traits such as patience and tolerance. In all, possessing a diverse teaching experience is valuable.

Result and Discussion

On the other end of the spectrum, it is important to determine if these abilities produce and reflect desired results. This, of course, can only be demonstrated by students’ performance or quantitatively by students’ average grades. To ensure improvement on a larger rather than individual scale, paying attention to how teachers make use of and develop content from seminars is also a good way of determining teachers’ abilities. When studies on teachers’ methodologies and pedagogies are carried out, the competencies of teachers are measured along the lines of culture, gender, age, and mode of study.

Conclusion

In conclusion, no one basic form of teaching engages all students. No unique style of teaching helps to improve all learners at the same time. Helping students connect to content is key. One specific style of teaching is not enough. Instead, teachers are also encouraged to vary their methods of teaching and strategies for greater performance. Despite obstacles and barriers, students are required to work hard. They are expected to take delight in accomplishing their work. In all spheres, curiosity leads to learning. A variation in styles and methods of teaching ensures that students are not bored. Information adapted outside classroom learning means that students acquire a broad range of skills that ensure that they are not bored in the classroom. Overall, such styles (techniques) have been shown to be productive in classroom teaching. These include giving students positive feedback, encouraging students, making sure they believe they can do well, and giving students opportunities to prove themselves. Students should be given tasks that are not too difficult in each specific time frame; rather they should be challenging and not just proficient. All this depends on the personality of the teacher, and it is important to have these qualities in the teacher.

REFERENCES

1. Arkoudis, S., & Tran, L. T. (2010). Writing blah, blah, blah: Lecturers' approaches and challenges in supporting international students. *International Journal of Teaching and Learning in Higher Education*, 22(2), 169–178.
2. Fernandez, C. (2003). Learning from Japanese Approaches to Professional Development: The Case of Lesson Study. *Journal of Teacher Education*, 53(5), 393–405. <https://doi.org/10.1177/002248702237394>
3. Haines, P. (2019). *Developing Global Skills in ELT Classrooms*. ELTOC. *ELT Global Blog*. 2020. Oxford University Press ELT
4. Hashim, N. M. H. N., Alam, S. S., & Yusoff, N. M. (2014). Relationship between teacher's personality, monitoring, learning environment, and students' EFL

performance. *Journal of Language Studies*, 14(1). <https://doi.org/10.17576/GEMA-2014-1401-07>

5. Lamb, M. (2017). The motivational dimension of language teaching. *Language Teaching*, 50(3), 301–346. <https://doi.org/10.1017/S0261444817000088>

6. Miller, P. (2012). Ten Characteristics of a Good Teacher. *English Teacher Forum*, 50(1), 36–38. <https://doi.org/10.12968/prtu.2012.1.4.50>

7. Renandya, W. A. (2012). Teacher roles in EIL. *The European Journal of Applied Linguistics and TEFL*, 1(2), 65–80.